

Appropriating Motivational Strategies in the Classroom: Approaches to the 21st Century Educators

Janice G. Torrefalma, Adrian A. Sab, Ma. Wenavil Y. Omane,
Heide S. Omilig, Honeylane C. Legaspi

Faculty, Department of Education, Cebu, Philippines

ABSTRACT

The nature of motivation is vital to improving student learning outcomes. This research review explored the concept of motivational strategies of the teachers in elevating engagement and maximizing the learning growth of the students. Based on the gathered data, varied motivational strategies were employed by the teachers to meet the students' needs. Motivation and engagement, building a community in the classroom and mindset were labeled as the new approaches in maximizing the students engagement and learning beyond self. Further, Motivational strategies are highly influence on how students interact and engage in learning. Moreover, the students have elevated their responsibilities in the learning process due to awareness of their capabilities as an individual.

KEYWORDS: *Motivational Strategies, motivation, Mindset, Growth Mindset*

How to cite this paper: Janice G. Torrefalma | Adrian A. Sab | Ma. Wenavil Y. Omane | Heide S. Omilig | Honeylane C. Legaspi "Appropriating Motivational Strategies in the Classroom: Approaches to the 21st Century Educators" Published in International Journal of Trend in Scientific Research and Development (ijtsrd), ISSN: 2456-6470, Volume-4 | Issue-1, December 2019, pp.912-916, URL: www.ijtsrd.com/papers/ijtsrd29783.pdf

IJTSRD29783

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INRODUCTION

Motivation is a fundamental recipe for academic success. It involves internal and external factors that stimulate desire and energy in people to be continually interested and committed to job, role, or subject, or to make an effort to attain a goal. Dornyei (2001) argued that Motivation explains why individuals choose to accomplish something, how hard they are going to seek after it, and to what extent they are eager to continue the movement. In other words, motivation is the thing that makes you go, props you up, and figures out where you're attempting to go. Alderman (2004) indicates that Students with optimum motivation have a benefit because they have adaptive habits and strategy, such as preserving intrinsic value, setting goal and tracking themselves. (Pintrich, 1993).

Moreover, one of the most difficult aspects of becoming an educator is getting how to know how to motivate your students. It is additionally one of the most significant. Students who are not inspired won't adapt successfully. They won't hold data, they won't take an interest and some of them may even get problematic. An student might be unmotivated for an assortment of reasons. They may feel that they have no enthusiasm for the subject, discover the educator's strategies un-drawing in or be diverted by outside powers. It might even become known that an

understudy who seemed unmotivated really experiences issues learning and is need of unique consideration. While inspiring students can be a troublesome undertaking, the prizes are more than justified, despite all the trouble. Propelled students are progressively eager to learn and take part. Basically: Encouraging a class brimming with spurred understudies is pleasant for instructor and understudy the same. A few understudies are self-inspired, with a characteristic love of learning. Be that as it may, even with the understudies who don't have this normal drive, an incredible educator can make learning fun and motivate them to arrive at their maximum capacity. (TMD, 2019).

Wilcox (2018) Noted that teachers go through long stretches of difficult work and spend money to become specialists in their substance zones, with degrees and instructing affirmation to demonstrate it. We create educational program maps and instructing schedules to make certain to cover the fitting gauges. We suffer long stretches of expert advancement with the goal that we are knowledgeable in all the current instructive teaching method. We work together with partners so we are for the most part utilizing accepted procedures in the homeroom. We create appraisals for understudies with the goal that we can keep tabs on their development. At the point when this doesn't work, we have

deliberate intercessions planned for getting understudies in the groove again. What's more, student are as yet coming up short. The issue is that numerous student are not roused to learn. Indeed, even with the ideal exercise plan set up, an unmotivated understudy won't learn. A few educators guarantee that persuading student isn't their activity. It is an instructor's business to know the substance and to encourage it well; the student must assume liability for their learning and discover their own inspiration. This good old thought is the thing that points of confinement numerous instructors to being normal. An incredible educator perceives that understudy inspiration is fundamental for achievement in learning and that instructors are in the ideal situation to improve student inspiration.

Daggol (2013) stated that motivation has been main focus among educators during the time since it establishes the foundation of learning process. Learning is a convoluted and dynamic procedure, and learning in genuine sense gets finished through inspiration. Since will to learn fabricates one of the essential components of learning, understudies make a significant stride headed straight toward learning through inspiration.

Moreover, Ken (2017) the unmotivated student really is exceptionally energetic with regards to homework - he's spurred to evade it. Understudies are without a doubt inclined to need inspiration in school for an assortment of reasons. (Pelletier, Dion, Tucson, and Green-Demers, 1999) It has been resolved that people may encounter a nonappearance of inspiration to perform. There is a conviction that an enormous number of people don't have the individual capacity to authorize the necessary assignment, the conviction they can't keep up the exertion that is required by the conduct or the conviction that they are essentially weak in effectuating a reasonable result.

Moreover, academic motivation might be normal for school exercises that are not articulations of one's self or of one's qualities. On the off chance that school is depreciated, it prompts wrecking outcomes that definitely bring about persuasive shortfall. Students who interpret their surroundings as a transport of negative data about the estimation of school are increasingly inclined to create persuasive issues. Qualities should be investigated so as to totally comprehend academic practices (Bigelow & Zhou, 2001).

According Ford et al. noted that Motivating students isn't a simple task, however it is unquestionably a compensating when instructors effectively draw in their understudies in the correct way. Daggol (2013) expressed that inspiration is one of the significant keys to progress. Considering students' age, level, premium and requirements, rolling out a couple of improvements in the method for instructing and helping students remove fun from exercise add to inspiration and successful learning. Besides, inspirational convictions are exceptionally basic to the academic accomplishment of students since they help to decide the degree to which understudies will consider, esteem, invest exertion, and show enthusiasm for the assignment.

MOTIVATION

Research has shown that there are basically two types of motivation, namely extrinsic and intrinsic motivation. It's imperative to comprehend that we are not no different; in

this way successfully spurring students necessitates that you increase a comprehension of the various kinds of inspiration. Such an understanding will empower you to all the more likely comprehend your students. Extraneous inspiration alludes to rewards that are gotten not from the movement, however as an outcome of the action (Morris and Maisto, 2002). Extrinsic motivation emerges from the utilization of outer rewards or influences, for example, nourishment, acclaim, available time, cash or indicates a movement (Morris and Maisto, 2002), applies where the motivating forces are for the most part outside, in that they are independent from the individual and the assignment. Then again, inherent inspiration as indicated by Morris and Maisto (2002) emerges from inside components, i.e., it is because of remunerations given by a movement itself. As indicated by Krause et al (2003), intrinsic motivation emerges from interior factors, for example, a student's regular inclination of interest, urgent, certainty and fulfillment when playing out an undertaking.

Shrestha (2017) noted that Motivation can be characterized as an explanation (or reasons) which drives a person to act with a specific goal in mind. The marvel of motivation isn't restricted to simply people, and happens in each life form living. The reasons may not generally be the equivalent between two people acting with a specific goal in mind, yet pretty much every activity is coordinated by certain inspiration. Intrinsic and Extrinsic motivation are totally interestingly with one another in the way they work. To put it plainly, characteristic inspiration alludes to getting spurred from within or self-motivation. Then again, extraneous inspiration alludes to the inspiration caused on account of outside variables.

Importance of Motivation to Students

According to Merideth (2019) Motivation to learn connects with progress at school. That's the reason numerous guardians and educators are worried about helping understudies become progressively inspired in the homeroom. Educators who make exercises fascinating to children and assist students with getting amped up for school can cultivate a deep rooted love of learning and urge understudies to defeat impediments and discover achievement. It may be the case that students are interested, an exercise is fun, the point is intriguing and drawing in, or the errand gives them a chance to exhibit their qualities. Student inspiration both commonly and normally has to do with the understudy's longing to take an interest in the learning procedure. Inspiration mirrors the reasons or objectives that underlie their association or non contribution in academic activities. (Lumsden, 1994). Greater initiative, tenacity, and self-discipline are needed to take courses in the online environment than in the traditional classroom (Mandernach, et al., 2006).

Importance of Motivation to Teachers

Rosati (2017) stated that a persuaded instructor is pivotal to a fruitful homeroom. They will take a gander at educating through an alternate focal point, and, in doing as such, spur their understudies in their adapting as well. Inspiration empowers, coordinate and support positive conduct over a significant stretch of time. It includes moving in the direction of objectives and fitting exercises to accomplishing this reason. It likewise drives inventiveness and interest, starting the craving required for understudies to need to find out additional. Siggh (2018) Motivation is vital in any field you

work, in your every day schedule to do extraordinary things. On the off chance that you are not spurred to accomplish something, you can't give your best in that field. Teaching is a significant field as future improvement of our country is in the hand of educators. On the off chance that they themselves are not inspired, in what manner will they roused the understudies to accomplish extraordinary outcomes, how to do incredible things throughout their life. The thing students adapts particularly rely upon how an instructor educates it.

Importance of Motivation in Education

In every classroom, the motivation of the pupils within a class is paramount for a teacher, for them to be able to learn effectively and also to maintain a steady order on their behaviour. Tohidi (2012) noted that powering people to achieve high levels of performance and overcoming barriers in order to change". Motivation is the driver of guidance, control and persistence in human behavior. Motivation is of particular interest to educational psychologists because of the crucial role it plays in student learning. Motivation in education can have several effects on how students learn and how they behave towards subject matter. Because students are not always internally motivated, they sometimes need situated motivation, which is found in environmental conditions that the teacher creates.

OBJECTIVE OF THE STUDY

There is no denying that motivation is one of the most essential elements in achieving the overall objectives of educational institutions. Further, the nature of motivation is vital to improving student learning outcomes. In the past decade, several international studies have examined the issue of teachers' motivational strategies, as a result of the growing concern for student learning enhancement worldwide. This paper will gather information on the best motivational practices that teachers utilize across the globe.

RESULTS AND DISCUSSIONS

Motivation is of particular interest to educational psychologists because of the crucial role it plays in student learning. However, the specific kind of motivation that is studied in the specialized setting of education differs qualitatively from the more general forms of motivation studied by psychologists in other field (Westbrook, 2005).

Motivation and Engagement

Motivating students is one of the significant difficulties educators face consistently. Conceptualized as understudies' vitality and drive to connect with, learn, work viably, and accomplish their potential at school, inspiration and commitment assume an enormous job to students greatest advantage and delight in school. (Martin, 2006).

shows the importance of motivation and engagement in motivating students to achieve the institutions objectives. The data revealed that establishing relationship between teachers and students is very fundamental. According to Marzano (2011) positive relationships between teachers and students are among the most commonly cited variables associated with effective instruction. If the relationship is strong, instructional strategies seem to be more effective. Kaufman et al. (2011) noted that improving students' relationships with teachers has important, positive and long-lasting implications for both students' academic and social development. Solely improving students' relationships with their teachers will not produce gains in achievement. However, those students who have close, positive and supportive relationships with their teachers will attain higher levels of achievement than those students with more conflict in their relationships. Followed by meaningful praise which revealed also as the importance factor in dealing with students. Praise works. In fact, educational research since the 1960s shows that students at every grade level and in every subject like to be praised for their work in the classroom. The empirical evidence from the research shows that praise can have a positive impact on both student academic learning and social behavior. In determining why praise in the classroom is not used more often, Gable et al. suggest that teachers may not have had the training through peer coaching, self-monitoring, or self-evaluating and may not feel comfortable in acknowledging positive students behavior consistently (Bennett, 2019).

On the other hand, constructive feedback play also a role in elevating the confidence of the students. Providing feedback means giving students an explanation of what they are doing correctly AND incorrectly. However, the focus of the feedback should be based essentially on what the students is doing right. It is most productive to a student's learning when they are provided with an explanation and example as to what is accurate and inaccurate about their work (Reynolds, 2013). When feedback is predominately negative, studies have shown that it can discourage student effort and achievement (Hattie & Timperley, 2007, Dinham). Therefore, teachers need to be careful when giving feedback to the students. Overall, the data revealed that motivation and engagement provide environment that embrace positive interaction and belongingness.

Building community of Learner in the Classroom

Schools and classrooms are where children spend a significant amount of time each week, and teachers have an opportunity to help their students make the most of that time together by developing a classroom community each day.

Figure 1

Figure 2

When students' basic needs, such as their sense of safety, are met, they are more likely to reach outside their comfort zone to take academic risks necessary to grow and learn. Figure 2 shows the importance of building community of learner in the classroom. Giving of assistance when difficulty arises got the highest mean. Followed by students and teachers involvement and teachers initiative to encourage students to participate and lead learning beyond their reach. Moreover, students and faculty working together in partnerships; students having an active role in co-creating curriculum with the teachers; and students acting as agents of educational change (Bergmark & Westman, 2016; Bovill, 2014; Bovill & Bulley, 2011; Cook-Sather et al., 2014). Zepke (2015) underlines that students' active participation, whether in classroom, in curriculum management or in partnerships with other stakeholders, may open for acknowledging critical active citizenship as well as students' social well-being, beyond measurable outcomes and high achievement. According to Hughes et al. (2012) noted that as a teacher we need to give students a lots of opportunities to respond in class, and many different ways to participate. Not only does this get every student more actively engaged with your lesson, it also increases the amount of positive reinforcement they'll receive. Allow students with different strengths and needs to respond in different ways, such as speaking instead of writing and vice versa. Therefore, varieties of strategies does a teacher need to respond to students when dealing with a topic. Moreover, encouragement also play a vital role in motivating student to participate in the learning process. Overall, building a community of learner is a necessity to ensure that students are well developed not just the cognitive but also their overall capability.

Mindset

Mindsets are students' beliefs about learning and school. Students with learning mindsets are more motivated to take on challenging work, persist in the face of setbacks, and achieve at higher levels. Research shows that the following learning mindsets play a role in students' persistence and achievement in school (MSN, 2015).

Figure 3

A child with a fixed mindset may not engage with the process of learning, believing that any challenges they face are due to a lack of natural talent, skill, or intelligence. They will approach learning and challenges with an "I'm not good at this" attitude (Bower, 2017). Figure 3 shows the kind of motivational mindset that teachers painted in the mind of the students. Growth mindset seen as powered with perseverance and hard work prevailed. According to Dr. Wreck (2017) when students have a growth mindset, they

take on challenges and learn from them, therefore increasing their abilities and achievement. When students understand they can get smarter they exert more effort in their studies. Developing a growth mindset isn't easy, however it is achievable with time and effort. Students develop a growth mindset by recognizing that the brain isn't a fixed entity and that improvements can be made through learning new information. Growth mindset can be developed in the classroom by providing students with a range of different strategies that help improve the way they work and their ability to cope with pressure. By teaching students multiple strategies you provide them with the tools to persevere when faced with difficulties IDL (2016). Overall, growth mindset must developed with the students to maximize their full potential to tap success.

Conclusion

Based on the result of this research, motivational strategies of the teachers are significantly important to attain the overall objectives of the school. Motivational strategies are highly influence on how students interact and engage in learning. Moreover, the students have elevated their responsibilities in the learning process due to awareness of their capabilities as an individual. Further, through motivational strategies employed by the teachers, there's a harmonious relationship between students and teachers inside the classroom and students to students relationship in the learning process.

Recommendation

It is very fundamental to adopt the 21st century approach in motivating students to elevate the probability of quality engagement and learning. Further to cater the needs and need development of the students, teachers must also developed their awareness on these practices to ensure effective instruction in the long run.

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